

From Routes to Resilience: Exploring Manila Jeepney Drivers' Demographics and Perspectives on Proposed Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP) through Thematic Analysis

Samantha Ashley M. Landayan¹, Allyah Paula B. Magtanong², Arabella Mae L. Palma³, Marc Joshua D. Rait⁴, John Cyril M. Ramos⁵, Ashley Jahzara B. Villar⁶, Mc Rollyn Vallespin^{7*}

^{1,2,3,4,5,6} Institute of Architecture and Fine Arts, Far Eastern University-Manila, Sampaloc, Manila, 1008, Metro Manila, Philippines

^{7*} Undergraduate Studies, Institute of Education, Far Eastern University-Manila, Sampaloc, Manila, 1008, Metro Manila, Philippines

ABSTRACT: The Department of Transportation (DoTr) introduced the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP) through Department Order No. 2017-011 as the Philippines pushed towards modernization. The program aims to improve the transportation system, but it also poses challenges to traditional jeepney drivers such as income instability and job loss. This study aims to understand the experiences and perceptions of jeepney drivers based in Manila regarding the PUVMP. It examines the drivers' income level, access to financial resources, access to social services, job security, and coping strategies with the proposed plan. The researchers used a qualitative-descriptive approach to describe and analyze the jeepney drivers' perceptions and coping strategies. The study highlights the drivers' resilience through hardships, the need for practical solutions, better government support, and recognition of locally made jeepneys to ensure economic stability for drivers facing challenges from the PUVMP. The recommendations emphasize the importance of exploring the complexities of societal issues, especially for those involving the marginalized sector, and how dissecting these issues can help raise awareness and develop critical thinking skills.

KEYWORDS: traditional transportation, livelihood preservation, jeepney drivers resilience, urban mobility, socioeconomic challenges, stakeholder perspectives, government initiatives

INTRODUCTION

Jeepneys are one of the most common modes of transportation found in the Philippines. It is known for its traditional creative designs, which date back to the 1940s and were adapted from American military vehicles during World War II (Roces, 2023). These traditional Jeepneys play an integral role in the culture of Filipinos, being an icon of creativity, an important source of income for thousands of drivers, and a crucial part of commuters' lives. As the Philippines pushed toward modernization, the Department of Transportation (DoTr) introduced a new program called the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP) through Department Order No. 2017-011 under the Duterte government in 2017. PUVMP was called to be implemented to make the Philippine transportation system more efficient, safer, and environmentally friendly. Under the pretext of the environmental damages and safety concerns caused by the traditional jeepneys, the modernization program also entails its phaseout and replacing them with imported modern jeepneys.

The lack of acknowledgment of the multi-factored problem of the traditional jeepneys and the downside of import-dependent solutions to the problem created a blind side to the jeepney modernization program (Mendoza, 2021). An estimated 200,000 jeepney units are on the verge of being phase-out and may potentially harm the drivers' primary source of income (Magramo, 2024). Despite the drivers' support of the modernization, the program still poses difficulties and challenges, including the cost and effort it will take them to transition to modernized jeepneys. The jeepney drivers have their own perceptions and concerns, which shows the program's complexity (Palatino, 2024). Understanding the effects of the proposed phaseout and evaluating the drivers' resilience provide insights for having targeted solutions and policies that align with their needs.

With jeepneys being a widely used form of transportation, the modernization program raises a problem that can also target the country's economy when viewed on a larger scale. Numerous drivers would lose their jobs due to being unable to keep up with the program's costs, which can also heighten the unemployment rate in the country's transportation industry. This can leave drivers and

operators dealing with several issues, including financial instability or poverty. According to Lanzagarita (2023), The effects of the modernization program not only affect the drivers but also have a significant impact on commuters as there will be fewer vehicles to accommodate the commuters on a daily basis. Additionally, the privatization of jeepneys will cause an inflationary hike in transportation fares that can affect consumers.

Traditional jeepney drivers are affected by the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP), which offers both opportunities and challenges. On the other side, the program provides sustainability and safety for everyone, which will help to create a more sustainable transportation system (Lu, 2024). To deal with the challenges of this modernization, it is essential to understand jeepney drivers' insights and experience. This research looks into the resiliency of Filipino traditional jeepney drivers despite the challenges presented by the government's Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP).

The Jeepney Modernization Program in the Philippines has a dual impact on the transportation sector. On one hand, the program aims to improve the transportation system to be more efficient and economically friendly. However, it poses challenges to the traditional jeepney drivers, such as income instability and job loss, highlighting the need for a balanced and mutually beneficial method for all stakeholders (Mendoza, 2023). Approximately 100,000 jeepney drivers go on strike in response to the Philippine government's plan to phase out traditional jeepneys and replace them with newer, cleaner models due to concerns about their livelihood and the high cost of modernization. They expressed their opinions on revising the plan with the drivers, operators, and passengers in mind (Beltran, 2023). Accusations were made towards the government stating that the modernization program is implemented for large enterprises and foreign investors to monopolize the Philippines' transportation system (Palatino, 2024). Modernization programs are not bad at heart, but they should not be used as an excuse to be forced upon those who will be negatively affected. The betterment of the country should be a collective effort, not something that leaves the jeepney drivers hanging on their own (Viernesto & Saavedra, 2023). Furthermore, the challenges that come with the implementation of modern jeepneys in the country affect multiple parties, including the drivers, passengers, operators, and manufacturers, highlighting their need for a smoother transition toward modernization (Andalencio et al., 2020).

The related literature needs to include the observance of how jeepney drivers adapt and show their resilience amidst the proposed implementation of jeepney modernization. Although perceptions of jeepney drivers were taken regarding the possible effects of the jeepney modernization plan, it lacks specification regarding their coping mechanisms, such as the current activities they are engaging in, to cope with the possible effects of the program as well as their future plans if the program is to be implemented.

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. To determine the demographic profile of the jeepney drivers in terms of:
 - a. Age
 - b. Jeepney route
 - c. Years of experience as a jeepney driver
 - d. Estimated daily income
2. To identify and analyze the master themes emerging from jeepney drivers' responses regarding their experiences and perspectives on the Proposed Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP), with a focus on understanding their suggestions for program improvement, specifically:
 - a. Financial stability
 - b. Jeepney modernization program
 - c. Activities and experiences
 - d. Resilience and adaptation in the face of change
 - e. Suggestions to make the program better

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a qualitative-descriptive approach to describe a phenomenon and focused on gaining insights regarding a poorly understood research area. This made it a suitable approach for exploring the complexities of the Jeepney Modernization Program and understanding the various aspects of jeepney drivers and how they affect their resiliency to withstand the modernization program. This method can be used in research that involves gathering data by administering interviews to answer questions about who, what, where, and how (Ayton, 2023). Interviews were used for data gathering to efficiently collect information about the drivers'

experiences, perceptions, and attitudes toward the Jeepney Modernization Program and provide insights into the various aspects of their job given the problem of the research issues (Reed et al., 2021). In addition, this method of qualitative-descriptive research allowed a more in-depth exploration of the respondents' perspectives, experiences, and coping strategies, providing detailed data covering the study's complexities (Ayton, 2023).

Moreover, this methodological approach allowed us to uncover valuable insights into their occupation by describing factors regarding their profile, status, and occupation. Furthermore, to address the potential limitations such as "researcher bias" and the time-consuming qualitative data analysis, proper methodological ethics were utilized, such as reflecting biases, discussing with peers, and thoroughly examining the data to ensure the credibility and validity of the findings. Glesne (2016) states that this approach enables flexibility and openness to topics and insights. It is also particularly suitable for research areas with little prior knowledge. Overall, this approach offers a valuable framework for exploring the intricacies of the perceptions of the jeepney drivers on the Jeepney Modernization Program.

The participants were ten (10) traditional Philippine jeepney drivers based in the city of Manila, Philippines. The target participants were limited to a smaller sample size as the study focused on jeepney drivers whose routes were based around the city of Manila. This includes five (5) jeepney drivers from the Divisoria to Morayta route and five (5) jeepney drivers from the Divisoria to the Baclaran route. With the study having a specific area of interest, a purposive sampling technique was utilized to gather respondents and select jeepney drivers based on their routes, ensuring in-depth data gathering. The purposive sampling technique is used when a study has a specific area of interest or group to investigate with a clear purpose rather than a random one (Heath, 2023).

Moreover, interviews were utilized, and the researchers, guided by a prepared questionnaire, asked the chosen interviewee a series of questions regarding the topic of the study. The questionnaire used in this study was modified from similar research conducted by Atos et al. (2021) titled "Modernized Tradition: Transformation of Public Transport." The questionnaire consisted of thirteen (13) questions. It was designed to obtain their views on the program, their livelihood, their current activities as the program is being implemented, and their plans once the phaseout of the traditional jeepney starts.

The researchers also asked for the participants' approval to record the whole interview (Bos, 2020). Researchers aimed to standardize data collection procedures by providing clear instructions. Participants' privacy was ensured through confidentiality measures (Bos, 2020). After all the interview data was collected, the researchers proceeded with the data analysis, using a statistical and logical approach to describe and explain the data methodically. After gathering the data, thematic analysis was utilized to evaluate the different insights of the jeepney drivers on the modernization program. The information was broken down into different points and themes that helped the researchers analyze the data from various perspectives. Thematic analysis was beneficial in the study as it is useful for subjective information such as personal views and opinions (Jansen, 2023). Through this technique, the findings from the data gathering were easier to assess as statements with the same themes were organized accordingly. As for the software tool, Dovetail was used to help assess the data through a thematic analysis.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The questionnaire used in this study was modified from similar research conducted by Atos et al. (2021) titled "Modernized Tradition: Transformation of Public Transport." The original questionnaire went through revisions to align with the study's objectives. Modifications like language adjustment and item wording were made to better understand and communicate between the researchers and the drivers during the interview. The questionnaire consisted of thirteen (13) questions. It was designed to obtain their views on the program, their livelihood, their current activities as the program is being implemented, and their future plans once the phaseout of the traditional jeepney starts.

During the data-gathering procedure, the questionnaire was utilized through an interview and was divided into three (3) sections. Section I was dedicated to introducing the study, its significance, and its proponents. Section II was dedicated to the jeepney drivers' demographic profile and background necessary for the study. Section III was focused on the jeepney drivers' financial stability. Section IV was focused on their perceptions regarding the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP). Lastly, Section V was dedicated to the drivers' resilience amidst the proposed implementation of PUVMP.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the gathered data, this section presents the findings and discussions regarding the perspective of jeepney drivers and their resilience amidst the jeepney modernization program. Through thematic analysis of the data from the interviews, the master themes of the driver's response to financial stability, their perception of the modernization program, their activities and experiences, their resilience and adaptation to the phaseout, and their suggestions were formed. The analyzed data gives insight into understanding the jeepney driver's experiences, perceptions, situations, and coping strategies with the implementation of PUVMP.

Table 1. Demographic Profile

Respondent	Nickname	Age	Jeepney Route	No. of years being a Jeepney driver	Estimated Daily Income
1	Gilbert	48	MCU-Divisoria	8	2000
2	Epifanio	43	Morayta-Divisoria	4	800
3	Juvelino	46	MCU- Divisoria	21	700
4	Robin	32	Morayta-Divisoria	12	1500
5	Reynaldo	52	MCU- Divisoria	33	1500
6	Arnold	54	Morayta- Divisoria	30	500
7	Jimmy	52	Morayta- Divisoria	27	1500
8	Pedro	52	MCU- Divisoria	20	900
9	Ruben	66	Morayta- Divisoria	26	1000
10	Joseph	48	MCU- Divisoria	25	1000

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the Jeepney drivers, which indicates their age, jeepney route, number of years of being a Jeepney driver, and estimated daily income. This suggests that the starting age of the respondents when they started working as jeepney drivers was 20 years old and above. Their estimated daily income ranges from 500-2000 pesos, which is mostly spent on their daily needs, paying bills, and paying for the cooperative they are in. As Manual (2019) stated, the amount jeepney drivers gain in their livelihood is sometimes too little to support their daily necessities. Thus, if the PUVMP is to be implemented, they will have to take out loans and incur additional debt.

Table 2. Master Themes from Jeepney Drivers’ Response Regarding their Financial Stability in the Context of the Jeepney Modernization Program.

Master Themes	Corresponding Codes	Exemplar Quotes
	Vulnerability	<p>Verbatim: “Minsan nga kulang e lalo na kung nangungupahan ka pa. Wala na dahil ito lang ang hanap buhay ko, wala din naman hanap buhay asawa ko. Sakin lang din umaasa.”</p> <p>Translation: “Sometimes it's not enough, especially if you're still renting. It's gone because this is the only work I have, and my wife doesn't have work either. They only depend on me.”</p>
FINANCIAL RESOURCES	Financial Strain	<p>Verbatim: “Ang mindset ng driver pag kumita ngayon, bibigay lahat, magagastos lahat kase ang katwiran namin mayroon namang kinabukasan. Para kaming mga one day millionaire.”</p> <p>Translation: “As a driver, I have a mindset that my earnings for the day will be spent entirely for that same day to sustain our needs. We believe that there is still a next day to earn money to spent for the other days. We’re like one day millionaire.”</p>
	Financial Assistance	<p>Verbatim: “Nung pandemic, si yorme lang, local government pero sa national wala. nakakuha ako noon ng dalawang sakong bigas saka 4,000 pesos.”</p> <p>Translation: “During the pandemic, I was able to receive help from the local government like the 2 sacks of rice and 4,000 pesos. Other than that, none, even from the national government.”</p>
GOVERNMENT SUPPORT	Neglected	<p>Verbatim: “Parang wala silang ginagawang tulong sa aming mga driver para matulungan kami sa phase-out.”</p> <p>Translation: “We jeepney drivers don't seem to have gotten any help from the LGU, they don't seem to be doing anything to help us drivers to help us in the phase-out.”</p>

Table 2 presents the financial struggles of the jeepney drivers once they faced the Jeepney Modernization Program. It reflects the difficulty of earning money, as their family solely relies on them. Some jeepney drivers are financially strained because they must budget properly. According to Reynaldo, one of the jeepney drivers, “Sapat naman yung kinikita kaya patuloy kaming lumalaban dahil sa ganyan, eh kaya lang proyekto ng gobyerno.” (These circumstances are difficult because it's a project by the government). Jeepney drivers believe that they are forced to comply since they have nothing against the government. The study of Mendoza (2023) focuses on the experiences of jeepney drivers in Metro Manila amidst the jeepney modernization program. It presents similar narratives of financial challenges and the drivers’ obligation to comply with government requirements despite their socioeconomic status and difficulties. In summary, jeepney drivers need support to address their financial burden and ensure financial stability.

Table 3. Master Themes from Jeepney Drivers’ Response Regarding their Perception of the Jeepney Modernization Program

Master Themes	Corresponding Codes	Exemplar Quotes
CHALLENGES AND CONCERNS	Financial Burden on Drivers	<p>Verbatim: “<i>Para sa kin hindi maganda yang phase-out program na yan kasi maliban sa mahal na nga yung ipapalit na jeep masasayang pa lahat ng ginastos para sa jeep na meroon kami ngayon</i>”</p> <p>Translation: “For me, that phase-out program is not good because apart from the fact that the jeep to be replaced that are expensive, everything spent for the jeep we have now will be wasted.”</p>
	Fare Increase	<p>Verbatim: “<i>Pag nagmodernized tataas lang yung pamasahe, kawawa lang yung mga commuters.</i>”</p> <p>Translation: “If the modernization program happens, the fares would just go up and the commuters would be the ones on the short end of the stick.”</p>
	Shift of Workload	<p>Verbatim: “<i>Kasi may kota silang hinahabol. Hindi tulad namin dito, makuha lang namin ang boundary, hawak na namin oras namin, nakakapagpahinga kami ng maayos.</i>”</p> <p>Translation: “Because they are chasing a quota. Unlike us here, we just get the boundary, we have our time, we can rest properly.”</p>
	Unemployment	<p>Verbatim: “<i>Yung phase-out mahirap po matuloy e, kasi maraming kaming mga driver na mawawalan ng hanapbuhay e, unang una katulad sa kin may edad na ako, mahirap na tyaka na hindi na ko pwede makapasok pa sa mga ibang company.</i>”</p> <p>Translation: “The phase-out is difficult to happen, because many of us drivers will lose our jobs, like me, I am old and at this age it’s difficult to get other jobs.”</p>

Table 3 indicates the perceptions of the PUV drivers regarding the Jeepney Modernization Program. As presented in the table, the drivers anticipate various challenges and concerns once the program happens. These include the loss of jobs, financial strain, and heavier workloads. This can take a toll on the drivers, especially since this is mostly where their main occupation and source of income are. Most of the respondents are worried that due to the price of the modern jeepneys, they would not be able to keep up with the program which can result in them losing or shifting occupations as one driver states, “*Yung phase-out mahirap po matuloy e, kasi maraming kaming mga driver na mawawalan ng hanapbuhay e, unang una katulad sa kin may edad na ako, mahirap na tyaka na hindi na ko pwede makapasok pa sa mga ibang company* (The phase-out is difficult to happen, because many of us drivers will lose our jobs, like me, I am old and at this age it’s difficult to get other jobs.) Drivers participating in protests expressed concern that if the regulation of the Jeepney Modernization Program persists, it could lead to the unemployment of 600,000 Jeepney drivers and 300,000 operators (Ballaran, 2017). In summary, the respondents show a deep concern about how these challenges that the PUVMP poses will greatly impact the lives of many PUV drivers and commuters.

Table 4. Master Themes from Drivers Regarding Activities and Experience Related to the Jeepney Modernization Program

Master Themes	Corresponding Codes	Exemplar Quotes
INVOLVEMENT	Protesters	Verbatim: “Sumasali ako (sa mga protesta)” Translation: “I join the protests.”
	Leadership	Verbatim: “Chairman ako ng kooperatiba, tinayo ko yan para makasurvive kami” Translation: “I am the chairman of a cooperative, I created this to ensure we can survive.”
	Compliance to Cooperatives	Verbatim: “Hindi ako sumasali sa anumang aktibidad ah tulad ng pagpro- testa dahil una etong jeepney ko ay nakarehistro na sa mga cooperative ng jeep at pinagbabawalan nila kaming sumali sa mga ganitong aktibidad” Translation: “I don’t participate in any activities like protests since my jeep is registered in a cooperative and they prohibit us from joining those activities.”
NONINVOLVEMENT	Lack of Interest	Verbatim: “Hindi eh, pumapasada lang ako, kumbaga naghihintay nalang ako kung matutupad o hindi yang program ana yan” Translation: “No, I just drive and wait if the program happens or not.”
	Loss of Interest	Verbatim: “Noon sumasali ako pero ngayon hindi na, wala namang mangyayari” Translation: “I used to, but now I don’t since nothing will change.”

Table 4 indicates the drivers' involvement in the present activities being done by the traditional jeepney drivers to withstand the challenges posed by PUVMP. As shown in the table, some respondents stated that they participated in the protest to stop the jeepney phaseout. Aside from this, one of the respondents stated that he started a cooperative to lessen the burden on his fellow drivers and to ensure their survival. On the other hand, some drivers still choose not to get involved in any activities for different reasons. Two respondents stated that the cooperative they joined prohibits them from joining these types of activities.

In some cases, they lack the interest to do anything, as one driver states, “Hindi na ko sumasali kasi wala rin namang mangyayari” (I do not participate because nothing will happen). The stake of losing their livelihood pushes the drivers to participate in protests and join cooperatives as they face the challenges of the jeepney phaseout (Bernal & Ko, 2023). To sum it up, the respondents show that protesting is the most accessible way to mitigate the challenges of PUVMP, but due to how the program progresses, some choose not to be involved.

Table 5. Master Themes from Jeepney Drivers’ Response Regarding their Resilience and Adaptation in the Face of Change

Master Themes	Corresponding Codes	Exemplar Quotes
RESILIENCE	Adaptation	<p>Verbatim: "Kung saan yung hangin, doon nalang muna ako kasi walang kasiguraduhan sa lahat eh. Sa ngayon, naghahanap ako ng medyo maganda-gandang hanapbuhay na driver pa rin kaso kahit mga trucking nalang basta maganda ganda ang sahod."</p> <p>Translation: "I will just probably go along the flow of the wind because nothing is decided as of yet. As of now, I'm trying to find a better job, still as a driver, maybe for trucks, as long as the pay is well."</p>
	Coping Mechanism	<p>Verbatim: "Kung mapapatupad man tong phaseout siguro tutulungan ko na lang yung asawa ko mag tinda sa morayta tatal wala naman kaming magagawa bilang driver kung desisyon naman ng gobyerno ituloy ang phase-out."</p> <p>Translation: "If this phaseout is implemented, maybe I'll just help my wife's shop in Morayta, after all, we can't do anything as drivers if the government decides to continue the phase-out."</p>
	Relocation to Cooperative	<p>Verbatim: "Siguro yung pag hihirap kakayanin nalang namin... kung may malilipat na ano, pag natuloy yung phase-out, dun sa cooperative, diba yung may consolidation sila na sinasabi, kung ma aaply yan edi aaply kami pero syempre mahihirapan din kami kasi sa dami dami ng driver na mawawalan ng hanapbuhay."</p> <p>Translation: "We'll probably just endure the hardships... if there's a relocation, if the phase-out pushes through, to the cooperative, right? They mentioned consolidation, if that applies, then we'll apply too, but of course, we'll also have a hard time because many drivers will lose their livelihoods."</p>
	Concern about Job Loss	<p>Verbatim: "Wala na, magtatrabaho nalang ang hirap naman din kasi sa kompanya ang tagal tagal ng sahod... Kaya mas gusto ko pa din ang jeep."</p> <p>Translation: "It's gone, we'll just have to work, but it's hard because companies take a long time to pay... That's why I still prefer jeepneys."</p>

Table 5 indicates various responses of Jeepney drivers about their emotions and strategies in the face of the modernization program. The respondents exhibit resilience and adaptability as they navigate their challenges. Some of the respondents seek better opportunities elsewhere, such as trucking. Other respondents consider coping mechanisms, such as helping their spouses set up shops. There is also a recognition of potential relocation to their cooperatives, assisting them throughout the process. Some respondents show a lack of readiness in adapting and planning to the modernization program and remains silent and waiting for the program to be implemented as stated, "Kung saan yung hangin, doon nalang muna ako kasi walang kasiguraduhan sa lahat eh." (I will probably go along the flow of the wind because nothing is decided yet.). In a display of despair and resilience, traditional jeepney drivers and its outskirts converged in a transport strike, not only a protest of the phase-out program but also a call from souls at the brink of losing their livelihoods (Sornito, 2024). In summary, among the respondents, there is a visible concern about losing their jobs and the difficulty in finding alternative sources of income. Such concerns highlight the drivers’ attachment to their current professions for economic security despite the challenges the program brings them.

Table 6. Master Themes from Jeepney Drivers’ Response Regarding their Suggestions to Make the Program Better

Master Theme	Corresponding Codes	Exemplar Quotes
MODERN UPGRADE	Government support	<p>Verbatim: “Sana matulungan kami ng gobyerno dahil kami ay nagigipit at napipilitan dahil wala kaming choice, kami yung naiipit kasi kapag hindi kami nag comply doon sa modernization ay mawawalan kami ng hanap buhay.”</p> <p>Translation: “I hope the government will help us because we are being pressured and blinded because we have no choice, we are the ones being pressured because if we don't comply with modernization, we will lose our livelihood.”</p>
	Recondition	<p>Verbatim: “Siguro ipagawa nalang yung mga bulok na sasakyan kase tumatakbo pa naman, ipaayos nalang.”</p> <p>Translation: “They should just fix the old traditional jeepney units since those are still working.”</p>
	Patronage of locally made Jeepneys	<p>Verbatim: “Sa tingin ko mas mabuti yung jeep na gawang Pilipinas pa rin na mas inimprove kesa sa yung imported pa, kasi pag imported pa ang mamahal pa ng piyesa tapos galing pang ibang bansa eh edi pag imaintenance yun matagal pa, hindi katulad netong jeepney dali-dali lang ayusin, local pa.”</p> <p>Translation: “I think it's better to have a Philippine-made jeep that is improved than an imported one because if it's imported, the parts will be more expensive and that they're from another country, so maintenance will be hard and may take a long time, it's not like a jeepney that it's easy to fix and still local.”</p>
STATUS-QUO	Discontinue	<p>Verbatim: “Ang sa akin, hindi nalang sana matuloy yung phaseout. Yung kahit individual ka makakapagrehistro ka, hindi yung dadaan ka pa ng isang kooperatiba bago ka pa makapagrehistro.”</p> <p>Translation: “I hope the phaseout will not happen. I think it’s better if an individual can register without having to be part of a certain cooperative.”</p> <p>Verbatim: “Unang una ang sakin lang eh yung hindi maituloy, pero wala rin tayo magagawa kung yan ang gusto ng gobyerno ngayon, wala kaming choice kundi sumunod nalang kami.”</p> <p>Translation: “First of all, for me, I’d choose not to implement the program, but we have no choice if that’s what the government wants right now, us drivers, we don’t have a choice but to follow them.”</p>
	Apathy	<p>Verbatim: “Alam mo, kung mayroon man akong suggestion hindi ko sasabihin kase malaking kalokohan yan, tinuruan ko lang sila.”</p> <p>Translation: “If I had a suggestion, I would not even share it because this (modernization program) is just nonsense.”</p>

Table 6 indicates Jeepney drivers' various suggestions to improve the modernization program. Some respondents agreed to upgrade traditional jeepneys by fixing old pieces and machines, investing in locally made jeepneys, and gaining support from the government. On the other hand, other respondents expressed their disagreement with the implementation of jeepney modernization. In contrast, one respondent stayed apathetic and stated, "*Alam mo, kung mayroon man akong suggestion hindi ko sasabihin kase malaking kalokohan yan, tinuruan ko lang sila.*" (If I had a suggestion, I would not even share it because this (modernization program) is just nonsense). As Dychangco (2023) explained, the alternative solution that the government should give is to help traditional jeepneys comply with DOTR specifications rather than impose requirements that necessitate huge investments when it knows they are beyond the means of jeepney drivers and operators. In summary, respondents suggested the discontinuation of the PUVMP if Jeepneys were to be bought from other countries. Investing in locally made jeepneys or simple upgrading will do.

CONCLUSION

After the interviews with the jeepney drivers, the respondents shared their viewpoints and difficulties regarding the jeepney modernization program. The jeepney drivers' perspectives cover their financial struggles while defending their jobs as drivers. Despite their difficulties with the proposed jeepney modernization, the drivers expressed resilience in their determination to provide for their family's financial needs. Jeepney Drivers showcased various answers and provided suggestions for improving the program, highlighting the importance of government and agency support and the value of locally made jeepneys. In conclusion, the jeepney drivers' narratives emphasize the need for practical solutions and better government and government agencies' support to ensure the drivers' economic stability amidst the modernization program's challenges.

RECOMMENDATION

After the interviews with the jeepney drivers, the respondents shared their viewpoints and difficulties regarding the jeepney modernization program. The researchers have made the following recommendations in light of the findings and conclusions:

For future teachers, it is significant to incorporate studies regarding contemporary issues, such as the Jeepney Modernization Program, into learning materials. By doing so, educators can make students more aware of the various complexities of society and help foster a more critical approach to different issues. Educators should help students develop critical thinking skills and urge them to look for potential solutions to contemporary issues. Moreover, integrating real-world problems into learning materials can aid students in looking at issues from different perspectives, including those from the marginalized sector, and help them progress into making inclusive and unprejudiced solutions.

Many drivers cannot afford loans, so the price of obtaining a modernized jeepney ought to be lowered. To enable the drivers to acquire a unit would benefit the jeepney drivers. The number of modernized jeepneys and the employment rate of drivers will increase as a result.

This study is available for future researchers with similar topics to download/view using the link provided (https://docs.google.com/document/d/e/2PACX-1vT88uVjuo3Ygep_YTf9d8p_BwQRUyIKwNE5JKn3zNq1wigumPyCrrAwQSSaK6ZxKA/pub) and gain more insights.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Before anything else, we would like to thank God, the source of wisdom and inspiration that helped us persevere in this study. We offer our deepest appreciation for your guiding us through the complexities of the research with patience and reverence. Second, we want to express our gratitude to our family and friends for their unwavering support each day and for encouraging us to be motivated during the entire time we spent working on this research paper. We also want to express our gratitude to all of the jeepney drivers who voluntarily took time out from their work to participate in this study as our respondents. We would also like to extend our deepest gratitude to our professor, Mc Rollyn Vallespin, who honed our skills in analyzing the technicalities of the paper. His expertise, lessons, and insightful feedback helped us complete this study.

REFERENCES

1. Andalecio, A. P. Et Al. (2020). Implementation, challenges and stakeholders' perception of modernized Jeepneys in Metro Manila. IOPscience. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1529/3/032067>

2. Ayton, D. (2023). Chapter 5: Qualitative descriptive research. Oercollective.caul.edu.au. <https://oercollective.caul.edu.au/qualitative-research/chapter/unknown-5/>
3. Ballaran, J. (2017, October 17). Drivers in protest: Costly modernization to drive us to unemployment | Inquirer News. INQUIRER.net. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/938539/piston-transportation-strike-jeepney-modernization-drivers-operators-unemployment>
4. Beltran, M. (2023 March 8). Philippines Jeepney strike drives home modernisation concerns. Aljazeera. <https://www.aljazeera.com/amp/news/2023/3/8/jeepney-strike-drives-home-concerns-about-modernisation-plan>
5. Bernal, B. & Ko, F. (2023 December 8). Fears of losing livelihoods mount as Manila's jeepney drivers protest phase-out of iconic vehicles. CNA. <https://www.channelnewsasia.com/asia/fears-losing-livelihoods-mount-manila-jeepney-drivers-protest-phase-out-iconic-vehicles-philippines-4013926>
6. Bos, J. (2020). Confidentiality. In *Springer eBooks* (pp. 149–173). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-48415-6_7
7. Dychangco, B. (2023 March 8). [OPINION] The jeepney phaseout as a cultural issue. Rappler. <https://www.rappler.com/voices/thought-leaders/opinion-jeepney-phaseout-cultural-issue/>
8. Glesne, C. (2016). *Becoming qualitative researchers: An Introduction*.
9. Jansen, D. (2023, October 26). *What (Exactly) is thematic analysis?* Grad Coach. <https://gradcoach.com/what-is-thematic-analysis/>
10. Lanzagarita, P. (2023, November 28). *This is Why We Shouldn't Phase Out Jeepneys* — Art+ Magazine. Art+ Magazine. <https://artplus.ph/features/this-is-why-we-shouldnt-phase-out-jeepneys>
11. Lu, B.J. (2024) *Navigating the landscape of jeepney modernization*. Philippine News Agency <https://www.pna.gov.ph/opinion/pieces/813-navigating-the-landscape-of-jeepne-modernization>
12. Mendoza, R. L. (2023 March 7). The Future of Jeepney Modernization in the Philippines: Impacts, Challenges, and Opportunities. Golden Haven. <https://www.goldenhaven.com.ph/blog/the-future-of-jeepney-modernization-in-the-philippines/>
13. Mendoza, T. (2021 February). Addressing the Blind Side of the Government's Jeepney Modernization Program. UPCIDS.
14. Palatino, M. (2024 January 2). Filipino Jeepney Drivers Make Last Stand. The Diplomat. <https://thediplomat.com/2024/01/filipino-jeepney-drivers-make-last-stand/>
15. Reed, M., Ferré, M., Martín-Ortega, J., Blanche, R., Lawford-Rolfe, R., Dallimer, M., & Holden, J. (2021). Evaluating impact from research: A methodological framework. *Research Policy*, 50(4), 104147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2020.104147>
16. Roces, I. (2023, March 11). The jeepney phase-out explained. Manila Bulletin. <https://mb.com.ph/2023/3/10/the-jeepney-phase-out-explained>
17. Sornito, I. (2024, February 1). LIFELINE ON THE LINE: Jeepney drivers say transport modernization threatens livelihoods. Panay News. <https://www.panaynews.net/lifeline-on-the-line-jeepney-drivers-say-transport-modernization-threatens-livelihoods/>
18. Viernesto, K., & Saavedra, S. (2023, April 21). #OPINION | Jeepney modernization: An erasure of livelihoods. Medium. <https://medium.com/the-science-scholar/opinion-jeepney-modernization-an-erasure-of-livelihoods-1089e4a8d270>

Cite this Article: Samantha Ashley M. Landayan, Allyah Paula B. Magtanong, Arabella Mae L. Palma, Marc Joshua D. Rait, John Cyril M. Ramos, Ashley Jahzara B. Villar, Mc Rollyn Vallespin (2024). From Routes to Resilience: Exploring Manila Jeepney Drivers' Demographics and Perspectives on Proposed Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP) through Thematic Analysis. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 7(5), 2502-2512